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PRINCIPLES OF INVESTIGATING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE PERIODICAL PRESS AND THE LITERARY PROCESS IN B. QOSIMOV'S RESEARCH

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Abstract. The article extensively examines Professor Begali Qosimov's views on mass media, particularly on the periodical press, and analyzes the influence of Jadid journalism on the social life of the country. The study investigates the scholar's perspectives on how newspapers and journals published by the Jadids reflected various aspects of life in Turkestan and explores his views on the formation and historical development of the Jadid press in the region.

Keywords: Jadid press, manifesto, Jadidism, national idea, Jadid criticism.

INTRODUCTION. It is well known that the Jadid press reflected issues related to the life of the region, national development, and the formation and advancement of national literature and Jadid journalism. As noted: "Literary criticism, which is intended to analyze literary phenomena and individual works of writers, explain their value to a broad audience, and cultivate the aesthetic taste of the public, addresses its readers through the periodical press. This characteristic becomes especially evident during the emergence of new eras in the history of a people and its literature. The history of Uzbek Jadid criticism at the dawn of the twentieth century—the period of national awakening—as well as Uzbek literary criticism on the eve of independence and during the first years of independence, provides vivid evidence of this fact."

In his studies, Professor B. Qosimov emphasizes that Jadid journalism emerged as a result of the relative freedoms granted by the October 17 Manifesto of 1905. Alongside the Uzbek-language publication *Turkiston Viloyatining Gazeti* ("The Newspaper of the Turkestan Province"), Ottoman Turkish, Caucasian, and Volga-region press traditions played a significant role in its development. Although periodical publishing in Turkestan had appeared earlier, in 1870, Qosimov points out that the press of that period largely served the military-colonial policies of the Russian Empire. Examining the opinions of contemporary specialists on Jadid journalism, he notes that Ziyoy Said mentioned the publication of 45 newspapers and 36 journals between 1870 and the 1920s. Qosimov argues that the Jadid movement at the beginning of the twentieth century successfully directed the press toward socio-political objectives. Therefore, he pays particular attention to periodical publications of the era. While studying Jadid journalism, the scholar stresses the special influence of Tatar journalism on the emergence of Jadidism in Turkestan.

Among the publications that gained prominence were *Al-Asr al-Jadid* (1904), *Qozon Muxbiri* and *Nur* (1905), and *Ulfat*, *Ishchilar Dunyosi*, *Ulug' Turkiston*, *Yulduz*, and *Ozod* (1906). He especially highlights the newspaper *Vaqt*, which achieved considerable fame throughout the Muslim East.

The author of the first Tatar novel, *Hisomuddin Mulla* (1886), Musa Aqyigit, after studying in Turkey, published the newspaper *Mulkiya* and the journal *Mir'at* between 1900 and 1908. The well-known writer Fatih Karimi later served as editor of *Vaqt*. According to Qosimov, this newspaper devoted significant attention to Turkestan and covered a wide range of topics, from Uzbek architecture to literary, historical, cultural, administrative, and socio-political issues.

He notes that articles portraying Turkestan realistically were published under such pseudonyms as "From the Editorial Office or Traveler," "A Traveler," "Samarqandi," "A Man from Bukhara," "A.F.," "Brother," and "Correspondent." In particular, the article "Turkiston Tuproqlari" ("The Lands of Turkestan") criticized Russian colonial policy and lamented the fact that the transformation of Turkestan into an extension of Inner Russia had failed to awaken the local population from political apathy. The spirit of solidarity, according to Qosimov, was a def

LITERATURE REVIEW. Professor **B. Qosimov** emphasizes in his studies that Jadid journalism emerged as "a result of the certain freedoms granted by the October 17 Manifesto of 1905." He notes that, alongside the Uzbek-language publication *Turkiston Viloyatining Gazeti* (*The Newspaper of Turkestan Province*), the press traditions of the Ottoman Turks, the Caucasus, and the Volga region also played a significant role in its development. Periodical press in Turkestan had actually appeared earlier, in 1870, before the Jadid movement. However, Qosimov points out that during that period the press mainly served the military-colonial policy of the Russian Empire. While examining contemporary specialists' views on the press of the Jadid era, the scholar writes that "when Ziyo Said discussed newspapers and journals published between 1870 and 1920, he mentioned the names of 45 newspapers and 36 journals" [2, p. 53].

Qosimov argues that the Jadid movement of the early twentieth century successfully directed the press toward socio-political objectives. For this reason, he pays particular attention to the journalism of that period. While studying Jadid publications, he notes the especially strong influence of the Tatar press on the emergence of Jadidism in Turkestan. He highlights such publications as the journal *Al-Asr al-Jadid* (1904), the newspapers *Qozon Muxbiri* and *Nur* (1905), and *Ulfat*, *Ishchilar Dunyosi*, *Ulug' Turkiston*, *Yulduz*, and *Ozod* (1906), emphasizing that the newspaper *Vaqt* gained particular fame throughout the Eastern world [3, p. 51].

The author of the first Tatar novel, *Hisamuddin Mulla* (1886), **Musa Oqyigit**, returned from studies in Turkey and published the newspaper *Mulkiya* as well as the journal *Mir'ot* between 1900 and 1908 [4, pp. 198–200]. The well-known writer **Fatih Karimi** served as editor of *Vaqt* in 1907. In his research, Qosimov notes that this newspaper paid considerable attention to the life of Turkestan, covering a wide range

of topics from Uzbek architecture to literary-historical, cultural-administrative, and socio-political issues.

The scholar also points out that the newspaper published articles portraying the realities of Turkestan under such pseudonyms as “On Behalf of the Editorial Office or Traveler,” “A Traveler,” “Samarqandiy,” “Buxoroli,” “A.F.,” “Qardosh,” and “Correspondent.” He discusses how the article *Turkiston Tuproqlari* (*The Lands of Turkestan*) by “Yo‘ldosh O‘g‘li” criticized Russian colonial policy, lamenting that Turkestan’s transformation into an internal colony of Russia had failed to awaken its people from political apathy. According to Qosimov, the spirit of solidarity constituted the central theme of these publications [5, p. 53].

Furthermore, the newspaper published articles by Turkestani Jadids such as Mahmudxo‘ja Behbudiy’s *Faryodi Turkiston* (*The Cry of Turkestan*) and *Duma va Turkiston Musulmonlari* (*The Duma and the Muslims of Turkestan*), as well as Abduqodir Shakuriy’s *Turkistonda Maktab va Tarbiya* (*Schools and Education in Turkestan*). Qosimov emphasizes that Behbudiy sharply criticized the poor state of education and enlightenment in the region, as well as administrative practices based on corruption.

Analyzing Behbudiy’s article *The Duma and the Muslims of Turkestan*, Qosimov notes that it expressed concern over the restriction of the political rights of Turkestanis. As an example, Behbudiy pointed out that although six representatives were elected from the 70,000 Europeans living in the region, only five seats were allocated to the local population of seven million people [6, p. 54]. Qosimov interprets this criticism as evidence that the Jadids paid close attention to every political process affecting society.

In addition, the scholar examines both major and minor newspapers and journals of the period and evaluates their significance. For example, discussing publications from smaller cities such as *O‘qlar* (*Arrows*) in Uralsk (June 1, 1907) and *Idil* in Astrakhan (September 7, 1907), he notes that S. Sunchalay and S. Ramiyev were active contributors to *Idil*, while Abdulla To‘qay regularly contributed to *O‘qlar*. Among journals such as *Ong*, *Tarbiya*, *Yashin*, *Yalt-Yult*, *Sho‘ro*, *Cho‘kich*, *O‘qlar*, and *Tarbiyat ul-Atfol*, he identifies *Sho‘ro* as the most prominent.

Qosimov notes that *Sho‘ro* was published twice a month in Orenburg from 1908 to 1918, producing a total of 240 issues. The journal was founded by the industrialist brothers Zokir and Shokir Ramiyev, and edited by the educator and religious scholar Rizoiddin Faxriddin. According to Qosimov, the journal’s significance lay in its attention to the ideological foundations of Jadidism and the everyday issues of national awakening. Based on researcher Sh. Soatova’s analysis of the contents of all 240 issues of *Sho‘ro*, he concludes that the journal’s materials were remarkably diverse in both genre and theme [7, p. 56].

Qosimov further states that inspired by the 1905 Manifesto, the Turkestani press made significant progress within a short period and attracted the attention of influential circles throughout the Turkic world. He notes that Cho‘lpon was among

the first to acknowledge this achievement [8, p. 2]. Drawing on **Abdulla Avloniy's** article *The History of Early Uzbek Periodical Press*, Qosimov cites factual data showing that between 1905 and 1917, 22 newspapers and 8 journals were published in Uzbek in Turkestan [9, p. 115]. This demonstrates the steady development of the Jadid press and the emergence of an educated readership interested in newspapers and journals. As Jadid ideas spread through the press, they stimulated significant changes and innovations across all spheres of society.

In his studies, Qosimov identifies *O'rta Osiyoning Umr Guzarligi* as the first Uzbek-language newspaper and notes Avloniy's characterization of it as "somewhat free-thinking." He also emphasizes that *Taraqqiy*, published under the editorship of **Ismoil Obidiy** in 1906, became the first Uzbek national newspaper. He points out that June 27—the date of its first publication—was later declared "Press Day" by a resolution of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Thus, *Taraqqiy* occupied a special place in the Jadid movement, leaving a lasting mark in history as a publication that enriched national consciousness. Qosimov cites evidence showing that it became one of the most beloved newspapers among the people, as described by Avloniy. He also notes that the famous Tatar poet **Abdulla To'qay** was familiar with the newspaper, that **Ismoilbek Gaspirali** wrote an article entitled *Taraqqiy* congratulating his colleagues in Tashkent, and that both **Abdulla Avloniy** and **Munavvarqori** regularly contributed materials to the publication [10, p. 49].

Such observations allow readers to gain a deeper understanding of the literary and educational life of the period. Beginning publication on September 6, 1906, the newspaper *Xurshid* brought together young intellectuals such as **Abdulla Avloniy**, **Fansurullobek Xudoyorxonov**, **Muhammadxon Podshoxo'jayev**, and the brothers **Komilbek** and **Karimbek Norbekov**. Qosimov stresses that *Xurshid* was actively involved in political issues as well.

Analyzing Behbudiy's article *Xayrul Umuri Avsatuho* published in the sixth issue of the newspaper, Qosimov notes that it condemned the autocratic policies of the Tsarist government, including the confiscation of waqf properties, the destruction of madrasas, the resettlement of Russian peasants, and the resulting impoverishment of the local population, whose property and wealth increasingly fell into the hands of Jewish and Armenian communities. These developments were portrayed as symptoms of the nation's tragic condition.

Such bold criticism was an extraordinary phenomenon for its time. The fact that publicistic writings openly offered political assessments of society demonstrates, according to Qosimov, the high level of political consciousness and civic culture possessed by the Jadids.

he scholar notes that such publications did not last long; from December 1, 1907, the newspaper "Shuhrat" ceased publication, and shortly afterward the newspaper "Xurshid" also closed down at different times, after which new newspapers began to appear in their place [11, p. 110].

B. Qosimov, while agreeing with the view of some press historians that “in the early period of Jadid literature there were years of interruption due to the Tsarist government’s restrictions on freedom of speech and the press” [12, p. 62], identifies 1913 as the year when the press began to revive and reform again. He links the re-emergence of newspapers and journals in Turkestan with the efforts of Mahmudkhodja Behbudi. He notes that the newspaper “Samarqand”, edited by Behbudi, became a “midwife” for many later journals. The scholar emphasizes that this newspaper brought together Jadid “like-minded” intellectuals, including Siddiqiy Ajziy, Hoji Muin, Nusratulla Qudratulla, and Saidrizo Alizoda, and thus held a high status in its time.

One of the prominent Jadid newspapers was “Sadoyi Turkiston”. Professor B. Qosimov notes that it began publication on April 4, 1914. In each issue, poems or articles by leading Jadid figures such as Avloni were published, along with poems by Tashkent writers such as Munavvarqori, Miskin, Xislat, and Tavallo; from Samarkand, Vasliy and Hoji Muin; and from Fergana, So‘fizoda, Hamza, Cho‘lpon, Lutfulla Olimiy, and Ibrohim Davron. He states that this newspaper quickly became a leading publication that united all Jadid writers, but it ceased publication after issue 66 due to financial difficulties.

Later, a number of other newspapers appeared: Obidjon Mahmudov’s newspaper “Sadoyi Farg‘ona”, Munavvarqori’s “Najot”, A. Battol’s “Sho‘royi islom”, Avloni’s “Turon”, Fitrat’s “Hurriyat”, Zaki Validi’s “Kengash”, B. Soliyev and A. Zohiriy’s “El bayrog‘i”, K. Bakir’s “Ulug‘ Turkiston”, as well as “Ishtirokiyun”, “Qizil bayroq”, “Turkiston”, “Mehnatkashlar tovushi”, “Buxoro axbori”, “Mehnat bayrog‘i”, and “Farg‘ona” [13, p. 63]. Among these, “Hurriyat” is distinguished for its literary strength, while “El bayrog‘i” is noted for expressing the ideas of autonomy as a vivid page of the struggle for Turkestan’s independence.

The first journal published in Turkestan was “Oyna”. According to the scholar, it was published in 1913 through Behbudi’s initiative and efforts. It consisted of 68 issues and 1720 pages, played an important role in spreading national ideas, and introduced not only Uzbek writers but also the best representatives of the broader Turkic world. From the scholar’s views, it becomes clear that the Jadid press served as a means for the wide dissemination of Jadid literature.

While analyzing Alibek Husaynzoda’s 1909 article “Turkism – Militarism” published in the newspaper “Taraqqiy”, Professor Begali Qosimov notes that the writer advanced an important idea based on linguistic material. He explains that certain verbs expressing the imperative mood in the language contain 4–5 layers of command meaning (for example: ur, urdir, urdirt, urdirtir; chiq, chiqar, chiqart, chiqartir), which is not found in other languages. This multi-layered structure reflects the strict hierarchy of administrative systems that have existed since ancient times, based on strict subordination of ranks and positions. For example, the commander of an army would not directly say “Attack the fortress!” to soldiers but would say

“Make it be carried out!”, and this order would gradually pass through the ranks of commanders [14, p. 123].

Thus, even a single word is shown to have a significant role in society and in human life. The Jadids therefore placed language issues at the forefront, seeing national development, survival, and preservation as rooted in national identity. Alibek Husaynzoda emphasized that the language of every nation is a mirror of its life, thought, and spirit.

B. Qosimov systematically analyzes articles, critical essays, and writings on language, literature, and social life published in the periodical press. He evaluates Behbudi’s article “Tanqid saralamoqdur” (“Criticism is selection”) as an attempt, after several centuries of silence following Navoi, to define the essential features of criticism and raise the issue of equality in literature [15, p. 22].

B. Qosimov’s strong conclusions about the socio-political and literary-aesthetic views of Jadid writers are made possible through his thorough study of the periodical press. He explains that many articles in the press reflect a unified social thought, where issues ranging from personal freedoms to social justice were placed on the agenda of literature.

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The first journal published in Turkestan was "Oyna". According to the scholar, it was published in 1913 through Behbudi's initiative and efforts. It consisted of 68 issues and 1,720 pages, played an important role in spreading national ideas, and

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